

Inductive Voltage Transformer Behaviour in the Frequency Range from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz

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Abstract—With the widespread diffusion of power converters able to be directly connected to Medium Voltage (MV) grids, there is the need to measure high frequency distortion, that is from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz. Inductive Voltage Transformers (VTs) are still the most installed voltage transducers in the power systems, but the knowledge of their behaviour in this frequency range is still an open issue. The aim of this paper is to analyse the behaviour of inductive VTs from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz. A commercial VT has been tested and the results show that the nonlinearity of the iron core can influence the behaviour of inductive VTs at least up to 150 kHz.

Keywords—Instrument Transformers, Frequency Characterization, Nonlinear Behaviour, Medium Voltage, High Frequency Distortion.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the widespread adoption of renewable energy systems in recent decades, disturbances up to 150 kHz have increased in the power systems. These disturbances also occur at Medium Voltage (MV) levels and are mainly due to the harmonics of the frequency components around the switching frequencies of power converters (either loads or generators). These high-frequency components are usually referred to as High Frequency Distortion (HFD) or supraharmonics. Due to their negative impact on Power Quality (PQ), numerous challenges have emerged in various fields of electrical engineering. These challenges include identifying and accurately measuring these disturbances in order to find the sources and mitigate the effects. To accurately measure the electrical quantities in MV grids, voltage and current transducers are needed to decrease the voltage and current levels from MV to a compatible level for measuring instruments. The inductive Instrument Transformers (ITs), both Voltage as well as Current Transformers (VTs and CTs), are the most widely used transducers in power systems for

measurement and protection due to their numerous advantages, such as their accuracy at power frequency, reliability, low maintenance, safety features, and suitability for a wide range of applications. However, their performance degrades at frequencies different from power frequency. Therefore, the influence of the frequency behaviour of inductive ITs is crucial for: 1) assessing harmonic levels, 2) verifying compliance with compatibility levels and emission limits established in International Standards [1]-[3], not only for power frequency, and 3) verifying compliance of Power Quality Indices (PQI). The main problem is related to the nonlinear behaviour of the inductive ITs, which is influenced by several factors, such as magnetic saturation [4], hysteresis [5], eddy currents [6], and the relative variation of magnetic permeability with frequency [7]. In fact, several papers in the literature show that the nonlinear behaviour of inductive VTs up to 1 kHz influences the metrological performance [8]. In particular, when a transformer's magnetic core reaches saturation at the power frequency (50/60 Hz), it shows a strong nonlinear behaviour. In this frequency range, the main problem are the spurious harmonics due to the fundamental tone and hysteresis loop of ferromagnetic core. These frequency components are superimposed on the voltage harmonic components, and therefore, especially inductive VTs show errors in the order of some percents when measuring the harmonic components. However, in recent years, some compensation techniques have been designed to improve the metrological performance of VTs in measuring harmonic components up to 1 kHz [9], [10], [11]. Moreover, the nonlinear behaviour of ITs is influenced by the input signal. The superimposition of several PQ phenomena at the input of ITs, like subharmonics or interharmonics components, can strongly affect the measurement performances at harmonic frequencies [12], [13], [14]. Moreover, in recent years, some European research projects have focused on new methods for the frequency

characterization of ITs, in order to use them also for PQ applications up to 9 kHz [15], [16].

Although some papers deal with the frequency behaviour of inductive ITs up to about 10 kHz [17], their behaviour in the wider frequency range up to a few hundred kilohertz is not completely addressed. In particular, topics like the definition of test waveforms, accuracy parameters and procedures for the evaluation of the metrological performance of ITs (both inductive as well as Low Power, LPITs), the development of new systems for the generation of AC/DC voltages and currents with spectral components up to 150 kHz are open challenges [18], [19]. In addressing these challenges, there is a need to define accurate parameters for VTs and CTs and the related measuring instruments up to a few hundred kilohertz. These topics are among the objectives of the European Partnership in Metrology (EPM) 22NRM06 "ADMIT" [20], [21]. Moreover, the findings of the project will contribute to the development of new standards within the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) Technical Committee (TC) 38 "Instrument Transformers".

For what concerns the performance of inductive ITs over about 10 kHz, the behaviour of the iron core should be accounted. Literature [22], [23], [24], [25] shows the variability of relative magnetic permeability with frequency; since it depends on the used ferromagnetic material, in some cases it decreases quickly and in others it is very flat. Therefore, these different behaviours can strongly influence the performance of inductive ITs over 10 kHz.

This paper aims to analyse the behaviour of inductive VTs in the frequency range from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz.

The structure of the paper is as follows. Section II describes the implementation of the measurement setup. Section III provides the test waveforms and the metrological performance indices. Section IV presents some preliminary results related to the metrological performance of a commercial inductive MV VT. Finally, Section V draws the conclusions.

II. MEASUREMENT SETUP

A. Setup architecture

On the basis of a deep literature review, from the point of view of the measurement setup, it can be stated that the characterization of an MV VT or CT, in the frequency range from power frequency up to 150 kHz, is still an open issue. No National Metrology Institute (NMI) around the world is able, at least with a declared uncertainty, to do that.

For what concerns voltage, MV amplifiers that allow the simultaneous generation of the fundamental component (DC or AC 50/60 Hz) up to tens of kilovolts and high-frequency components, with reduced amplitude, are available on the market. However, their frequency range is limited up to 20 kHz [11], [12].

The solution used in this paper is the one proposed in [26]. It consists of the separate generation of the power frequency component (at 50/60 Hz) from the High-Frequency Components (HFCs). This can be done by using two different generators and by combining their outputs. The basic block diagram of the solution is shown in Fig. 1 (a). It proposes a classical characterization method based on the comparison [11], [12] of the outputs of a reference VT and of a VT under test, by means of a comparator.

Fig. 1. Basic block diagram (a) and picture (b) of the proposed measurement setup

From the point of view of generation, the basic block diagram in Fig. 1 can be implemented in different ways, depending on the used generators. For instance, if one of the two used generators presents a galvanic insulated output, the two generators can be connected in series to realize the sum of their outputs. Instead, if neither of the two has a galvanic insulated output, a parallel connection can be adopted, provided that suitable filters are used to prevent damage to both generators.

For the case at hand, the Power Frequency Generator (PFG) is obtained by means of an Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG), cascaded by a low-voltage amplifier, cascaded, in turns, by a step-up transformer to reach the required voltage levels. Instead, the high-frequency generator is obtained by means of an AWG, cascaded by another low-voltage amplifier, having an output frequency range from DC up to 150 kHz.

As it can be seen from Fig. 1, the sum of the PFC and of the HFC is simply obtained by the series connection of the output of the Step-Up Transformer (SUT) and of the High-Frequency Amplifier (HFA). In particular, one terminal of the HFA is connected to the ground, and the other is connected to the lower potential terminal of the SUT. This is possible thanks to the intrinsic galvanic insulated output of the SUT.

B. Setup implementation

The reference voltage signal to be applied to the VT under test is provided by two AWGs National Instruments (NI) PCI eXtension for Instrumentation (PXI) 5422 (16 bit, variable output gain, ± 12 V output range, 200 MHz maximum sampling rate, and 256 MB of onboard memory). The comparator is realized by using a multifunction I/O module PXIe-6124 (± 10 V, 16 bit, and maximum sampling rate 4 MHz), that acquires the primary and secondary waveforms of the VT under test. The AWGs use an 8 MHz clock to generate the waveforms and this clock is used to derive the sampling clock, chosen as 4 MHz; this allows obtaining coherent sampling, thus avoiding spectral leakage.

The output of the first AWG (AWG 1) is connected to an arbitrary four-quadrant voltage and current amplifier Bolab (± 75 V, ± 20 A, 1 kW, DC – 1 MHz) feeding the VT under test through a 100 V / 24 kV SUT. The output of the second AWG (AWG 2) is connected to a high-speed bipolar amplifier NF (± 150 V, 200 VA, DC – 500 kHz). The voltage range for the setup is equal to 24 kV for the fundamental component and to 100 V for high-frequency components. Primary voltages are scaled with a commercial high-voltage probe (HVP), that is the “Reference VT” in Fig. 2, having a scale factor of 1000:1 and uncertainties on ratio error of 15 mV/V (level of confidence 95%) from DC up to 5 MHz. A low-voltage divider (LVD), having a ratio of about 18.5 V/V and uncertainties on ratio errors of 10 mV/V (level of confidence 95%) from DC up to 150 kHz, has been designed and built for the measurement of the secondary voltage of the VT.

III. TEST WAVEFORMS AND PERFORMANCE INDICES

To evaluate the metrological performances of ITs in realistic conditions (that are conditions very similar to those that can be encountered in actual power systems), some authors of this paper have proposed several test waveforms to assess the frequency behaviour of ITs from power frequency up to 9 kHz [27], [28]. For sake of clarity, in the following a brief recall about possible test waveforms and measurement indices is provided. Without loss of generality, the indices refer to VTs; with minor modifications they can be adapted for CTs.

A. Fundamental component

The basic waveform for testing ITs is a virtually pure sinusoidal waveform. This test is already prescribed by the international standards [29]-[36], and it is thought to evaluate the ratio and phase errors at power frequency for the ITs accuracy class verification. According to the standards this test shall be performed at various primary amplitudes in several test conditions [37].

B. Fundamental component plus harmonic components

In order to obtain the frequency behaviour of ITs from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz, it is possible to use two kinds of test waveforms. At the moment this paper is written, two methods are the most acknowledged for the accurate characterization of inductive ITs [38], [39][39]. Both the methods involve realistic waveforms composed by the fundamental component at rated frequency and amplitude, plus other harmonic components with reduced amplitudes. The first method [38] (in the following named also FH1, that stands for Fundamental plus 1 Harmonic tone), includes also one sweeping harmonic tone, whereas the second method [39] (in the following named also FHN, that stands for Fundamental plus N Harmonic

tones), includes also a number of harmonic tones having random amplitudes and phase angles. However, the Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) and the amplitude of the harmonic components should not exceed the limit prescribed by the international standards [1], [2], [27], [30], [31].

C. Frequency behaviour performance indices

According to international standards, ratio and phase errors are the main indices for evaluating the frequency behaviour of VTs [27]. However, ratio and phase errors are defined at power frequency. These errors are extended here, assuming that phasors are evaluated at frequency f . Therefore, at each frequency, the ratio and phase errors can be evaluated by the following equations:

$$\varepsilon(f) = \frac{k_r V_s(f) - V_p(f)}{V_p(f)}, \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta\varphi(f) = \varphi_s(f) - \varphi_p(f), \quad (4)$$

where:

- $k_r = V_{p,r} / V_{s,r}$ is the rated transformation ratio ($V_{p,r}$ and $V_{s,r}$ are the rated primary and secondary voltages), evaluated at fundamental frequency;
- $V_p(f)$ and $V_s(f)$ are the RMS values of the primary and secondary voltages at frequency f , respectively;
- $\varphi_p(f)$ and $\varphi_s(f)$ are the phase angle of the primary and secondary voltages at frequency f , respectively.

Table I provides the expanded uncertainty (level of confidence 95%) for the whole test setup for amplitude and phase (u_ε and $u_{\Delta\phi}$, respectively).

IV. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

This section provides experimental results related to the characterization of a commercial inductive VT with rated primary voltage 3000 V, rated secondary voltage 100 V, rated burden 25 VA and accuracy class 0.5.

A. Frequency behaviour

The frequency behaviour of VT under test has been evaluated by means of FH1 test waveforms. Therefore, the generated test waveforms are made up of: 1) the fundamental component at 50 Hz; 2) one harmonic component. The amplitude of the fundamental component is chosen equal to 3 kV, whereas the amplitude of the harmonic component is chosen equal to 2 % of the fundamental tone, and its frequency varies from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. In the following, the frequency of the harmonic component will be referred to as f_{hf} .

Fig. 2 shows the frequency behaviour of $\varepsilon(f)$ and $\varphi(f)$ from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. It can be observed that the ratio error is within ± 20 % up to 50 kHz. A first resonance occurs at about 12 kHz, whereas a second resonance, having a lower entity, at about 60 kHz. The last observable resonance occurs over 150 kHz. The phase error is within -0.4 rad up to

TABLE I: EXPANDED UNCERTAINTY OF u_ε (μ V/V) and $u_{\Delta\phi}$ (μ rad)

	Frequency (kHz)									
	0.05		9		50		100		150	
	u_ε	$u_{\Delta\phi}$								
	(μ V/V)	(μ rad)								
U_c (95 %)	160	160	1300	1300	3200	4200	10000	8000	14000	12000

Fig. 2. Ratio and phase errors vs. frequency for the inductive VT.

150 kHz. With reference to the accuracy class extensions defined in [40] and reported in Table II, regarding the ratio error it can be observed that the inductive VT totally meets the requirements of WB1, whereas it completely misses the ones of WB2, WB3, and WB4. As regards the phase error, the inductive VT totally meets the requirements of WB1 and WB2, whereas it only partially satisfies the requirements of WB3 and WB4. The IEC 61869-1 ed.2 specifies that some extensions defined in [40] may not apply to some specific ITs. These results show that the extended accuracy class limit should not be applied to inductive VTs.

Even though these VTs are not designed to work at frequencies different from power frequency, Fig. 2 shows that ratio and phase errors are comparable to the limits of the extensions of the accuracy class of [40], at least up to 100 kHz. Therefore, considering only the frequency behaviour, one might conclude that the usage of such a VT could be extended far beyond its proper application, up to 100 kHz.

B. Spectral analysis

A deeper insight into the behaviour of the inductive VT under test can be provided by the spectral analysis of the input and output waveforms. Fig. 3 (Fig. 4) shows the input (output) spectrum for the case $f_{hf} = 10 \text{ kHz}$ in the range [9, 100] kHz.

Comparing the input and the output spectra, an element can be noticed.

In the output spectrum, the high-frequency tone is surrounded by a small “dome”, which is made up of components at frequencies equal to $f = f_{hf} \pm kf_1$ ($f_1 = 50 \text{ Hz}$, and $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$) (see Fig. 5). This phenomenon is

TABLE II: IEC 61869-1 ED.2 ACCURACY CLASS EXTENSIONS

Accuracy classes	Ratio error (+/-) at frequencies shown below		
	$0.05 < f \leq 1 \text{ kHz}$	$1 < f \leq 1.5 \text{ kHz}$	$1.5 < f \leq 3 \text{ kHz}$
WB1	$0.05 < f \leq 5 \text{ kHz}$	$5 < f \leq 10 \text{ kHz}$	$10 < f \leq 20 \text{ kHz}$
WB2	$0.05 < f \leq 20 \text{ kHz}$	$20 < f \leq 50 \text{ kHz}$	$50 < f \leq 150 \text{ kHz}$
WB3	$0.05 < f \leq 50 \text{ kHz}$	$50 < f \leq 150 \text{ kHz}$	$150 < f \leq 500 \text{ kHz}$
WB4			
0.1	1%	2%	5%
0.2 - 0.2S	2%	4%	5%
0.5 - 0.5S	5%	10%	10%
1	10%	20%	20%
Protection	10%	20%	30%

Fig. 3. Input waveform spectrum ($f_{hf} = 10 \text{ kHz}$) in the range [9, 100] kHz.

Fig. 4. Output waveform spectrum ($f_{hf} = 10 \text{ kHz}$) in the range [9, 100] kHz.

due to the intermodulation effect between the high-frequency tone and the fundamental component at 50 Hz. This effect is less relevant in the input waveform spectrum, reported in Fig. 6, therefore it is due to the inductive VT nonlinearity.

Therefore, in order to assess the impact of these phenomena, let consider an actual application of the tested VT, i.e. its field use to measure possible HFDs present in the grid. Let suppose, f.i., that the input waveform, which is an unknown quantity, is composed by the power frequency component and one high-frequency component, as in Fig. 3. According to the results shown in this Section, the VT output waveform would have a spectrum very similar to that shown in Fig. 4, so containing a number of spectral spurious components which are introduced by the VT itself. Therefore, if we use the VT output to measure the input, by simply scaling it even with a frequency dependent scale factor, the input waveform reconstruction would lose accuracy.

In some papers [27], [41], it is demonstrated that, due to the iron core nonlinearity, for inductive VTs at low frequencies (up to some hundreds hertz) a range should be associated to the ratio error at each frequency, rather than a single value. The results discussed here show that similar phenomena could affect the behaviour of inductive VTs also up to hundreds of kilohertz.

Fig. 7 (Fig. 8) provides the input (output) spectrum for the case $f_{hf} = 100 \text{ kHz}$. Comparing the output spectra of Fig. 8 ($f_{hf} = 100 \text{ kHz}$) and Fig. 4 ($f_{hf} = 10 \text{ kHz}$), the same phenomena are observable. This shows that this kind of observed behaviour does not significantly depend on the frequency f_{hf} .

Fig. 5. Output waveform spectrum [zoom around the injected tone ($f_{hf} = 10 \text{ kHz}$)].

Fig. 6. Input waveform spectrum [zoom around the injected tone ($f_{hf} = 10 \text{ kHz}$)].

C. Nonlinearity amplitude dependence

In order to evaluate how much the nonlinear phenomena observed in the previous section can depend on the fundamental component amplitude, three FH1 tests have been conducted. The fundamental component amplitude is varied from 80% to 120% of the rated VT voltage (that is, 3000 V), whereas the injected harmonic component is set at 2% of the fundamental tone, and its frequency is chosen equal to $f_{hf} = 10 \text{ kHz}$. The ratio between the Root Mean Square (RMS) of the spurious tones in the range [$f_{hf} - 1 \text{ kHz}$, $f_{hf} + 1 \text{ kHz}$] and the RMS of the injected harmonic tone ($f_{hf} = 10 \text{ kHz}$) has been chosen as an indicator of nonlinearities. The results are shown in Table III.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has analysed the behaviour of inductive VTs from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz. In particular, a commercial MV VT was tested by using realistic power system waveforms. Experimental results show that, in the considered frequency range [9 kHz, 150 kHz], inductive VTs can introduce intermodulation distortion between the power frequency component and the high-frequency ones. This demonstrates

TABLE III: NON-LINEARITY DEPENDENCE OF THE FUNDAMENTAL COMPONENT AMPLITUDE

Fundamental component amplitude (% of rated voltage)	$RMS_{spurious}/RMS_{f_{hf}}$
80%	0.283%
100%	0.401%
120%	0.678%

Fig. 7. Input waveform spectrum ($f_{hf} = 100 \text{ kHz}$) in the range [80, 300] kHz.

Fig. 8. Output waveform spectrum ($f_{hf} = 100 \text{ kHz}$) in the range [80, 300] kHz.

that attention must be paid when trying to reconstruct the input spectral content of an inductive VT by simply multiplying its output by VT's inverse transfer function. Further work is needed to state whether these high-frequency nonlinearities can limit the use of inductive VTs for measurements up to 150 kHz or not.

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REFERENCES

- [1] EN CEI 50160 Voltage characteristics of electricity supplied by public distribution networks'. CEI, May 01, 2011.
- [2] IEC 62749 Assessment of power quality - Characteristics of electricity supplied by public networks'. IEC, Feb. 11, 2020.
- [3] IEEE Std 1159 - IEEE Recommended Practice for Monitoring Electric Power Quality'. IEEE, 2019.
- [4] M. Beyranvand e B. Rezaeealam, «Finite Element Study of Ferroresonance in single-phase Transformers Considering Magnetic Hysteresis», Journal of Magnetism, vol. 22, pp. 196–202, giu. 2017, doi: 10.4283/JMAG.2017.22.2.196.
- [5] José Antonio Badri, Jordi-Roger Riba, Antoni Garcia, Santi Trujillo, Albert Marzábal, «Transformer modelling considering power losses using an inverse Jiles-Atherton approach», International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems, Volume 154, 2023, 109461, ISSN 0142-0615, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2023.109461>.
- [6] Vahidi, B., Naghizadeh, R.A. (2023). Transformer Core Modeling. In: Principles and Modeling of the Power Transformers. Energy Systems in Electrical Engineering. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-5796-5_4

- [7] M. Kaçki, M. S. Rylko, J. G. Hayes and C. R. Sullivan, "Magnetic material selection for EMI filters," 2017 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE), Cincinnati, OH, USA, 2017, pp. 2350-2356, doi: 10.1109/ECCE.2017.80964567.
- [8] G. Crotti et al., «How Instrument Transformers Influence Power Quality Measurements: A Proposal of Accuracy Verification Tests», *Sensors*, vol. 22, fasc. 15, 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22155847.
- [9] Cataliotti, A.; Cosentino, V.; Crotti, G.; Delle Femine, A.; Di Cara, D.; Gallo, D.; Giordano, D.; Landi, C.; Luiso, M.; Modarres, M.; et al. Compensation of nonlinearity of voltage and current instrument transformers. *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.* 2019, 68, 1322–1332
- [10] Crotti, G.; D'Avanzo, G.; Giordano, D.; Letizia, P.S.; Luiso, M. Extended SINDICOMP: Characterizing MV Voltage Transformers with Sine Waves. *Energies* 2021, 14, 1715. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14061715>
- [11] G. D'Avanzo et al., "Theory and Experimental Validation of Two Techniques for Compensating VT Nonlinearities," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 71, pp. 1-12, 2022, Art no. 9001312, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2022.3147883.
- [12] G. Crotti, G. D'Avanzo, P. S. Letizia and M. Luiso, «The Use of Voltage Transformers for the Measurement of Power System Subharmonics in Compliance With International Standards», *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 71, 2022, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2022.3204318.
- [13] Y. Chen et al., «Metrological performances of current transformers under amplitude modulated currents», in *IMEKO TC10 Conf. «Test., Diagn. Insp. Compr. Value Chain Qual. Saf.»*, International Measurement Confederation (IMEKO), 2019, pp. 101–106. [Online]. Disponibile su: <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85073286422&partnerID=40&md5=1c716b15b11594d73acb3f66f77ee9b>
- [14] G. Crotti, G. D'Avanzo, P. S. Letizia, e M. Luiso, «Measuring Harmonics with Inductive Voltage Transformers in Presence of Subharmonics», *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 70, 2021, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2021.3111995.
- [15] EMPIR 19NRM05 IT4PQ project website, <https://www.euramet.org/seg-it4pq1> (Available online on 4th December 2023).
- [16] <https://www.it4pq.eu/> (Available online on 10th January 2024).
- [17] I. Jayathilaka et al., "Calibration System for High-Voltage Transformers with Multiharmonic Distorted Waveforms," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 73, pp. 1-13, 2024, Art no. 1501013, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2024.3370744.
- [18] G. Crotti et al., «Characterization of Voltage Transformers for MV Applications Up to 150 kHz - A Preliminary Study», in *IEEE Int. Workshop Appl. Meas. Power Syst., AMPS - Proc.*, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., 2023. doi: 10.1109/AMPS59207.2023.10297174.
- [19] Letizia, P.S.; Crotti, G.; Mingotti, A.; Tinarelli, R.; Chen, Y.; Mohns, E.; Agazar, M.; Istrate, D.; Ayhan, B.; Çayci, H.; et al. Characterization of Instrument Transformers under Realistic Conditions: Impact of Single and Combined Influence Quantities on Their Wideband Behavior. *Sensors* 2023, 23, 7833. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23187833>.
- [20] EPM 22NRM06 ADMIT, https://www.euramet.org/news-events-seg/details-news?tx_news_pi1%5Baction%5D=detail&tx_news_pi1%5Bcontoller%5D=News&tx_news_pi1%5Bnews%5D=1743&cHash=3dee4ab74ccbada5c668e69d243abf8fc [Available online on 27th November 2023]
- [21] <https://www.admit-project.eu/> (Available online on 14th May 2024).
- [22] W. Wang, A. Nysveen, N. Magnusson, e R. Nilssen, «Fourier-based effective permeability for transformer iron losses computation under saturations», *IET Electric Power Applications*, vol. 14, fasc. 13, pp. 2609–2615, 2020, doi: 10.1049/iet-epa.2020.0315.
- [23] S. Kul, F. Anayi, e T. Meydan, «Experimental comparison of localised magnetostriction difference under sinusoidal and PWM excitations», *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, vol. 544, p. 168692, feb. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jmmm.2021.168692.
- [24] T. C. Batista, B. A. Luciano, R. C. S. Freire, W. B. Castro, e E. M. Araújo, "Influence of magnetic permeability in phase error of current transformers with nanocrystalline alloys cores", *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, vol. 615, pp. S228–S230, dic. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.jallcom.2013.11.110.
- [25] Barbisio E., Bottauscio O., Chiampi M., Crotti G., Giordano D., "Parameters affecting ferroresonance in LCR electric circuits", in *IEEE Transaction on Magnetics*, vol. 44 (6), art. no. 4526797, pp. 870 – 873, 2008, doi: 10.1109/TMAG.2007.916314.
- [26] G. Crotti et al., "Characterization of Voltage Transformers for MV Applications Up to 150 kHz - A Preliminary Study," 2023 IEEE 13th International Workshop on Applied Measurements for Power Systems (AMPS), Bern, Switzerland, 2023, pp. 01-05, doi: 10.1109/AMPS59207.2023.10297174.
- [27] G. Crotti et al., "Fast Frequency Characterization of Inductive Voltage Transformers Using Damped Oscillatory Waves," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 73, pp. 1-14, 2024, Art no. 9001714, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2023.3343773.
- [28] G. Crotti, G. D'Avanzo, C. Landi, P. S. Letizia and M. Luiso, "Evaluation of Voltage Transformers' Accuracy in Harmonic and Interharmonic Measurement," in *IEEE Open Journal of Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 1, pp. 1-10, 2022, Art no. 9000310, doi: 10.1109/OJIM.2022.3198473.
- [29] IEC 61869-1 Ed.2: Instrument Transformers – Part 1: General requirements, IEC, 2023.
- [30] IEC 61869-2 Instrument transformers - Part 2: Additional requirements for current transformers. IEC 2012.
- [31] IEC 61869-3 Instrument transformers - Part 3: Additional requirements for inductive voltage transformers. IEC 2011.
- [32] IEC 61869-6 Instrument transformers - Part 6: Additional general requirements for low-power instrument transformers. IEC 2016.
- [33] IEC 61000-4-30 Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) - Part 3-40: Testing and measurement techniques - Power quality measurement methods. IEC, 2015
- [34] IEC 61000-4-7 Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) - Part 4-7: Testing and measurement techniques - General guide on harmonics and interharmonics measurements and instrumentation, for power supply systems and equipment connected thereto». IEC, 2008
- [35] «IEC 60044-7 Instrument transformers - Part 7: Electronic voltage transformers». IEC, 1999.
- [36] «IEC 60044-8 Instrument transformers - Part 8: Electronic current transformers». IEC, 2002.
- [37] G. Crotti, G. D'Avanzo, C. Landi, P. S. Letizia and M. Luiso, "Evaluation of Voltage Transformers' Accuracy in Harmonic and Interharmonic Measurement," in *IEEE Open Journal of Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 1, pp. 1-10, 2022, Art no. 9000310, doi: 10.1109/OJIM.2022.3198473.
- [38] A. Cataliotti *et al.*, "Compensation of Nonlinearity of Voltage and Current Instrument Transformers," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 68, no. 5, pp. 1322-1332, May 2019.
- [39] M. Faifer, C. Laurano, R. Ottoboni, S. Toscani and M. Zanoni, "Harmonic Distortion Compensation in Voltage Transformers for Improved Power Quality Measurements" in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 68, no. 10, pp. 3823-3830, Oct. 2019.
- [40] IEC 61869 standard family "Instrument transformers".
- [41] M. Faifer, C. Laurano, R. Ottoboni, S. Toscani and M. Zanoni, "Characterization of Voltage Instrument Transformers Under Nonsinusoidal Conditions Based on the Best Linear Approximation," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 67, no. 10, pp. 2392-2400, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2018.2806949.